

THE IMPACT OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE ON EDUCATIONAL MANAGEMENT

Mukhlisa Abdulloeva

Teacher, TSUE

Abstract

This thesis analyzes the impact of artificial intelligence technologies on the education management system. The role of artificial intelligence in automating management processes, analyzing data, increasing the efficiency of decision-making in educational institutions, and improving the quality of education is highlighted. The opportunities and problems of implementing these technologies are also considered.

Keywords

education management, digital transformation, automation, education quality, data analysis, innovative technologies, e-learning, management efficiency, digital education.

The rapid development of information and communication technologies in the XXI st century is also having a significant impact on the education system. In particular, artificial intelligence (AI) technologies are creating new opportunities in the organization and management of educational processes. Currently, in many countries of the world, artificial intelligence solutions are widely used to improve the management of educational institutions, effectively use resources and increase the quality of education.

Educational management is a complex process in which coordination of activities between students, teachers, administration and other stakeholders is of great importance. Artificial intelligence allows you to optimize these processes, process large amounts of data and make accurate decisions.

Artificial intelligence is a set of technologies that allow you to perform certain tasks inherent in human mental activity through computer systems. AI technologies are used in educational management in the following areas:

- Analysis of student data;
- Monitoring the educational process;
- Forecasting academic results;
- Resource management;
- Automation of document circulation;
- Monitoring the quality of education[3].

For example, artificial intelligence-based programs can analyze student attendance, mastery indicators and activity and identify problem situations in advance. This allows the management of an educational institution to take prompt measures.

A large part of daily management activities in educational institutions is related to data collection, processing and reporting. Artificial intelligence significantly reduces time and labor costs by automating these tasks.

For example, with the help of electronic management systems:

- Class schedules are automatically created;
- Classroom distribution is optimized;
- Teacher workload is calculated;
- Financial reports are generated.

As a result, heads of educational institutions have the opportunity to pay more attention to strategic issues. This helps to increase management efficiency.

Making the right decisions is of great importance in educational management. SI technologies analyze large amounts of data in a short time and provide scientifically based recommendations to leaders.

For example, students' grades, attendance, and interest in subjects can be analyzed and future results can be predicted. On this basis, decisions can be made to improve curricula, organize additional classes, or change pedagogical approaches.

In addition, with the help of artificial intelligence, it is also possible to develop development strategies for educational institutions. Analytical systems assess the current situation and identify future needs in advance.

Improving the quality of education is the main goal of any education system. Artificial intelligence is also emerging as an important tool in this regard.

AI technologies:

Monitor educational outcomes;

Create individual learning opportunities;

Identify student needs;

Adapt educational materials;

Automate assessment processes[2].

As a result, each student will have the opportunity to receive education tailored to their capabilities and needs. This will help improve the quality and efficiency of education.

Along with the advantages of artificial intelligence technologies, there are also some problems. Firstly, the implementation of AI systems requires significant financial resources. Not all educational institutions can afford to purchase modern software and hardware.

Secondly, the issue of data security is relevant. Ensuring the confidentiality of information about students and teachers is one of the important tasks.

Thirdly, the insufficient formation of digital competencies of some teachers and leaders may hinder the effective use of SI technologies. Therefore, improving personnel skills and developing digital literacy is important.

In the future, artificial intelligence is expected to become an integral part of educational management. Intelligent management systems, virtual assistants, automatic monitoring platforms and forecasting programs will further increase the efficiency of educational institutions[4].

Also, innovative solutions based on artificial intelligence will help to organize the activities of educational institutions in a transparent, efficient and effective way. As a result of the acceleration of digital transformation processes, educational management will rise to a new level.

Artificial intelligence technologies are one of the important factors in the modernization of educational management. They allow for the automation of management processes, effective analysis of data, improvement of the quality of decision-making and improvement of educational outcomes. At the same time, when introducing technologies, it is necessary to take into account issues related to financial, technical and information security. In the future, the role of artificial intelligence in educational management will increase and will serve to increase the efficiency of the educational system.

References

1. O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining raqamli ta’limni rivojlantirishga oid qarorlari va farmonlari. – Toshkent, 2020–2025.
2. Xudoyberdiyev B. Ta’lim menejmenti nazariyasi va amaliyoti. Toshkent: Tafakkur, 2021. – 286 b.
3. Karimov I., Xolmatov U. Ta’limda raqamli texnologiyalar va innovatsiyalar. Toshkent: O‘qituvchi, 2022. – 215 b.
4. Abdullayeva M. Raqamli ta’lim va boshqaruv texnologiyalari. Toshkent: Fan, 2023. – 184 b.